

Table 4S. Clinical features of hospitalized adult patients with SARS-CoV-2 infection

Characteristic	Pre-intensive care n=3 (%)	Intensive care n=13 (%)	P value
Glycaemia			0.025
≤99mg/dl	2 (66.6)	0	
>99mg/dl	1 (33.3)	13 (100)	
IL-6			0.486
≤100pg/ml	2 (13)	7 (47)	
>100pg/ml	0	6 (40)	
Azotemia			0.257
≤50mg/dl	1 (6.7)	1 (6.7)	
>50mg/dl	1 (6.7)	12 (80)	
Albumin			0.007
≤3.5g/dL	3 (100)	1 (7.7)	
>3.5g/dL	0	12 (92.3)	
Procalcitonin T0			0.529
≤0,5ng/ml	3 (100)	9 (69.2)	
>0,5ng/ml	0	4 (30.8)	
Prothrombin activity			
>28s	2 (66.6)	13 (100)	
D-Dimer			
>500ng/ml	0	9 (69.2)	